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M3.6 - 3 PID Policy Alignment Workshops and Feedback Report

Work Package	WP3
Lead Author (Org)	Rene van Horik (DANS-KNAW)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Wim Hugo (DANS-KNAW) Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen (CSC) Joy Davidson (DCC) Gabriela Mejias (DataCite) Natascha van Lieshout (SURF) Josefine Nordling (CSC) Lassi Lager (CSC)
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Dissemination Level

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Versioning and contribution history

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0.9	27.05.2024	Rene van Horik (DANS-KNAW)	Suggestions of contributing authors processed
1.0	30.05.2024	Rene van Horik (DANS-KNAW)	Updated version

Disclaimer

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Introduction

PIDs are a key component of the FAIR data principles. A wide range of policies and services exist to manage and create PIDs within the research ecosystem. Work Package 3 of the FAIR-IMPACT project, titled Persistent identifiers, has the objective to “work with PID service providers and infrastructures to meet user needs, align with EOSC policy and maximize uptake”. Task 3.3 of this work package is focused on “EOSC PID policy alignment and support” and will produce Deliverable 3.5 “Guidelines for creating a user tailored EOSC compliant PID policy” in month 24 of the project.

To achieve T3.3’s goal, three workshops were organized. An overview of the three workshops is provided below as well as links to more detailed information on the workshops (valid as on May 10 2024). Fortunately, a number of these resources have an assigned persistent identifier and should remain available in the long term.

Workshop 1

EOSC PID Policy. Measuring Compliance

November 16, 2022. 16:30-18:00 CET. EOSC Symposium Prague.

This workshop, organized in cooperation with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, introduced the components of the developed methodology which assesses compliance with the EOSC PID policy. The EOSC PID policy was introduced and analyzed by determining which stakeholders are involved and how they are positioned within the PID landscape. Also qualitative and quantitative measures to evaluate policies were introduced. The participants of the workshop were asked to formulate which stakeholders and measures they thought were relevant. The result was relevant for the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) including services developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC.

Program and Presentations:

<https://symposium22.eoscfuture.eu/symposium/breakout-session-eosc-pid-policy-and-faircore4eosc/>

Blogpost:

<https://fair-impact.eu/articles-and-blogs/collaboration-persistent-identifiers-took-steps-forward-prague>

Workshop 2

EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices

November 21, 2023. 09:00-13:00 CET. Online

This workshop consisted of a series of presentations and three interactive breakout sessions. The main goal of the workshop was to look into adapting existing PID implementation best practices and applying them to specific domains as well as to look into obstacles to implement EOSC PID policy compliant PID solutions. The breakout sessions were aimed at using the CAT to guide improvements in the compliance in the following areas: (1) Research workflows for datasets, (2) Research workflows for publications, and (3) Research workflows for software.

Information and presentations: [EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices | FAIR-IMPACT](#)

Link to the slides: van Lieshout, N., van Horik, R., & Hugo, W. (2023). EOSC Compliant PID Implementations - Practical Guidelines for Implementing Best Practices. Webinar, 21 November 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245076>

Workshop 3

Workshop: Defining Criteria for Assessing PID Policies and Services

February 19, 2024. 09:00-12:00 GMT. Workshop at IDCC conference, Edinburgh.

PIDs are a key component of the FAIR data principles. A wide range of policies and services exist to manage and create PIDs within the research ecosystem. This workshop, organized by the [FAIR-IMPACT project](#), targeted towards PID service providers, PID managers, PID owners and PID policy makers, was aimed at supporting the adoption of FAIR-enabling services and technology, such as PID-related core components developed by the [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) project.

The goal of this workshop was to introduce a compliance assessment method to determine the characteristics of persistent identifier policies and services. In the workshop the FAIRCORE4EOSC project's approach to assessing PID compliance was presented, evaluation of PID policy criteria was carried out and ideas on how FAIR-IMPACT could provide support

for this endeavor were discussed. The results of the workshop will be utilized in the becoming support programme of FAIR-IMPACT for further developments.

Workshop program and presentations: IDCC workshop to present and discuss criteria to assess PID policies and services. Edinburgh. 19 February 2024. van Horik, R., Nordling, J., van Lieshout, N., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Lager, L., Hugo, W., & Davidson, J. (2024). Workshop: Defining Criteria for Assessing PID Policies and Services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10791006>

Blogpost: [fair-impact-highlights-during-idcc-2024](#)